

Implementation of E-learning based-STEM on Quantum Physics Subject to Student HOTS Ability

Irfan YUSUF¹ , Sri Wahyu WIDYANINGSIH¹ and Sri Rosepda Br. SEBAYANG¹

¹Jurusan Pendidikan Fisika, Fakultas Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan, Universitas Papua, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

E-learning media is one effective solution as a learning tool that could be implemented anytime and anywhere. Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) approach through the use of e-learning is expected to develop students Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS). This study aimed to measure students HOTS abilities through the use of e-learning based-STEM media in quantum physics courses. Through purposive sampling technique set sample research that is students who are in the program of quantum physics courses for ten people in the even semester 2017-2018 in Jurusan Pendidikan Fisika Universitas Papua. The instruments used are eight numbers of HOTS questions in the form of essays and questionnaires of student responses given after the lesson. The data analysis technique used was gain test to see if there was the improvement of HOTS student ability and hypothesis test through SPSS to know the difference of HOTS ability before and after learning, while student response questionnaire analysis is done through Rasch modeling using the Winstep program. The results showed that the value of N-gain (0.7) high category and Wilcoxon test significance value (0.004) indicating that learning of quantum physics through e-learning based on the STEM can improve students HOTS capability. Rasch modeling showed that in general the students strongly agree on the learning done. Therefore, the implementation of e-learning based on the STEM in quantum physics course could be used as one of the references to develop students HOTS capability.

Keywords: e-learning, HOTS, response, STEM

INTRODUCTION

The development of science and technology has penetrated in various aspects of life including education. Science and technology today have an essential role in education, in particular, to equip learners with challenges in the future. Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) is one alternative that can be applied in science learning to build a generation capable of facing various challenges in the 21st century. Science and technology cannot be separated from the concept of the STEM. Science can be found from the advent of technological products and the opposite, the development of science supports for the

emergence of various cutting-edge technologies. The life skills of learners must meet the needs of today's world that they must be able to work with IT and develop their thinking skills (Wahyuni and Zainnuri, 2017).

The ability to think or known as HOTS is very important to train to learners who are able to develop their abilities in problem solving. The ability HOTS of students is still relatively low in Department of Physics Education, Faculty of Teaching and Education, University of Papua. The low ability of HOTS is affected by lack of student learning motivation (Yusuf and Widyaningsih, 2018). Innovation in learning is essential to be done by educators to improve the motivation to learn that affects the HOTS ability of students. The use of technology can be one of the innovations in learning that can foster the motivation of learners (Suryani, 2017). The use of technology in learning can help learners to understand the material and encourage their perception and motivation to learn (Yusuf and Subaer, 2013; Yusuf, et al., 2015; Iksan and Saufian, 2017).

One of the uses of technology in learning is through the use of e-learning. Learning through e-learning is one of the means of transforming conventional learning into digital form. Utilization of e-learning can eliminate the limits of space and time that happened in education (Gunga and Ricketts, 2007). Learning through the use of e-learning can affect the ability of STEM learners and their interest in science lessons (Proudfoot and Kebritchi, 2017; Popovici and Mironov, 2015). Learning through e-learning can also create learning independence for learners and contribute positively to their learning experiences (Tubaishat and Lansari, 2011).

Therefore, it is necessary to apply e-learning based on the STEM in the quantum physics course to examine HOTS capability of students. The purpose of this study is to measure students HOTS capabilities through the use of e-learning based on STEM-media in quantum physics courses.

METHODOLOGY

This research was quasi-experiment research of one group pretest-posttest design. The purposive sampling technique was used to determine the sample of research which was the student of quantum physic program courses of 10 people in the even semester of 2017-2018 Department of Physics Education, Faculty of Teaching and Education, University of Papua. The instruments used were eight of HOTS questions in essays and questionnaires of student responses given after the lesson. Data analysis technique used was the N-gain test ($\langle g \rangle$) to measure whether there was an improvement of HOTS student ability. The N-gain test equation according to Hake (1998) as in equation (1).

$$\langle g \rangle = \frac{\% \langle S_f \rangle - \% \langle S_i \rangle}{100 - \% \langle S_i \rangle} \quad (1)$$

Where, $\langle g \rangle$ was a normalized gain, $\langle S_i \rangle$ was the average score of the pretest, and $\langle S_f \rangle$ is the posttest average score. N-gain improvement criteria are categorized according to Table 1.

Table 1. Normalized average score criteria

Value $\langle g \rangle$	Criteria
$\langle g \rangle > 0,7$	High
$0,3 < \langle g \rangle \leq 0,7$	Medium
$\langle g \rangle \leq 0,3$	Low

The effectiveness implementation of e-learning based on STEM in the quantum physics course on students HOTS ability could be known based on the effect size value as in equation (2).

$$d = (m_A - m_B) / \left[\left(\frac{sd_A^2 + sd_B^2}{2} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where d was the effect size, m_A was the mean value of posttest, m_B was the average value of pretest, sd_A was the standard deviation of posttest, and sd_B was the standard deviation of pretest (Hake, 2002). The effect size value was categorized based on the criteria as in Table 2 (Cohen, 1992).

Table 2. *Category of effect size*

Effect size	Category
$d < 0,2$	Small
$0,2 < d < 0,8$	Medium
$d > 0,8$	High

Hypothesis testing was done using SPSS program to know the difference between HOTS ability before and after learning. Determination of hypothesis testing technique begins with normality test and homogeneity test of data. If the data was normal and homogeneous distributed then the hypothesis tested through parametric technique. But, if not normal or not homogeneous then the hypothesis tested using non-parametric analysis. Student response questionnaire analysis was done through Rasch modeling using the Winstep program. Winstep provided various features that could help in analyzing respondent ratings. Rasch modeling could proceed more accurate analysis results that had so far been unrivaled by other analytical techniques (Boone, et al., 2014).

RESULT and DISCUSSION

This research begins with giving the pretest to students. Pretest aims to determine the first ability and difficulty faced by students, so hopefully can be done applying the appropriate learning. Preparation of learning begins with the preparation of learning materials into e-learning system includes Semester Learning Plan, material slides, assignments, and evaluation of learning. The material presented on e-learning consists of various reference books and virtual experimental facilities that can be run by students to understand more deeply related to the concept of quantum physics material being studied.

The course of quantum physics consists of abstract concepts and is difficult to describe directly because of its microscopic scope. One solution to explain the abstract material is to include virtual lab media into the e-learning system. The e-learning system can run a variety of media such as video, animation, and virtual experiment simulations that can be run directly by both teachers and learners (Gordillo, et al., 2013). The virtual lab media can be run directly by the learner to understand the experimental principle. Experiments that can be executed virtually by learners include black thing radiation experiments, photoelectric effects, and Compton effects. A virtual experiment can help learners to understand experimental principles like real experiments in a real laboratory. The virtual experiments were conducted with due to consideration to the limitations of laboratory facilities and infrastructure, the dangers posed when the experiments were conducted in a real laboratory, or simulations

performed before the experiments were performed (Azis and Yusuf, 2013). Figure 1 shows the initial appearance of e-learning in Department of Physics Education, Faculty of Teaching and Education, University of Papua and the online classroom display of quantum physics courses.

Figure 1. The use of e-learning in learning (a) initial appearance of e-learning in Department of Physics Education, Faculty of Teaching and Education, University of Papua and (b) display of online classes of quantum physics

The study of quantum physics through the utilization of e-learning allows learners to be able to explore and find themselves a concept. A wide variety of reference books and instructional materials are presented directly and accessible whenever and wherever they are both inside and outside the classroom. All students are actively involved in learning. This can be seen from the ongoing online discussions and their enthusiasm in completing the assigned task. Figure 2 shows the active involvement of all students in collecting their assignments online through e-learning.

Figure 2. Records of tasks completed by all students.

Students, in general, are actively involved in learning. Involvement is visible on each task was given that they can complete all the tasks and upload them directly through e-learning as in Figure 2. Each student can interact directly with e-learning account given as a class participant. Lecturers can directly provide an assessment of each task so that students can know the results of the assessment of the tasks they do. Learning through e-learning is very effective, and there is no limit between lecturers and students as well as students with whom they can interact in learning (Zhanga, et al., 2006). The use of e-learning can also create the independence of learners learn that they can perform activities to complete the task

independently through their respective accounts (J. K. Lee and W. K. Lee, 2008). Learning through e-learning can improve the thinking ability of learners because they are expected to seek and find themselves a concept (Saadé, et al., 2012; Muryani, et al., 2017)

Measurement of HOTS capability of students before and after learning through e-learning based on in quantum physics courses obtained the N-g value of 0.4 or is in the high category as shown in Table 3. This result shows that learning through STEM-based e-learning on the course of quantum physics is instrumental in improving students HOTS skills. HOTS demonstrate the learners' deep understanding of the learning material that has been studied (Tanujaya, 2016).

Table 3. The result of HOTS student ability test before and after STEM-based physics learning using e-learning media

	Pretest	Posttest	g	N-g	N-g Criteria
Average	33.3	72.0	38.8	0.7	High
Standard Deviation	13.4	40.4	21.1	0.3	

The effectiveness of learning through e-learning based on the STEM in quantum physics course on students HOTS capability is shown through the result of effect size test as shown in Table 4. The result of effect size calculation is obtained by 3.5 which shows that e-learning is effective in physics course quantum of students HOTS capabilities.

Table 4. Results of effect size testing to find out how much the effectiveness of learning through e-learning based on the STEM in the subject of quantum physics

Learning Outcome	Average	Standard Deviation	Effect Size	Category
Pretest	33.3	13.4	3.5	High
Posttest	72.0	20.4		

Table 4 also shows that the average of pretest and posttest learning outcomes of students has increased from $33.3 \pm SD 13.4$ to $72.0 \pm SD 20.4$. The improvement of learning outcomes indicates that the performed learning improves students HOTS capabilities, although the standard deviation of posttest high is 20.4. This is because there is one student with the same value when the pretest and the value are very low compared with other students who have increased. The low learning outcomes of students are due to lack of activity during learning and often do not follow lectures online. Student activity can be traced directly through the use of e-learning as each student has their account and is known when they are active (Blas and Fernández, 2009).

The result of normality test data obtained sig value. Pretest and posttest respectively are 0.025 and 0.007 less than 0.05 indicating that the data is not normally distributed. Homogeneity test results obtained sig value. 0.566 bigger than 0.05 indicating that the data is homogeneous. Based on the result of the prerequisite test, it is found that the data is not normal but homogenous so that the non-parametric testing technique is done through Wilcoxon test as in Table 5.

Table 5. Wilcoxon test results of HOTS capability of students before and after STEM-based physics learning using e-learning media

	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks		Posttest - Pretest	
Negative Ranks	0 ^a	0.00	0.00	Z	-2.666 ^b	
Posttest - Pretest	Positive Ranks	9 ^b	5.00	45.00	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.008
	Ties	1 ^c				
	Total	10				

Wilcoxon test probability is 0.004 (below 0.05), and the students perception is general learning well so it can be concluded that e-learning is effectively used in the quantum physics lecture and has the real effect to increase students HOTS capability. The study of quantum physics through the utilization of e-learning allows learners to be able to explore and find themselves a concept. A wide variety of reference books and instructional materials are presented directly and accessible whenever and wherever they are both inside and outside the classroom. All students are actively involved in learning. Learning through e-learning is very effective, and there is no limit between lecturers and students. The implementation of e-learning based on the STEM in quantum physics course could be used as one of the references to develop students HOTS capability.

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REFERENCES

- Wahyuni, D. S. and Zainnuri, H. (2017). Boostering Students' Life Skill through IT Based Project Learning. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research (ASSEHR)*, 158(2017), 319-328.
- Yusuf, I. and Widyaningsih, S. W. (2018). Profil Kemampuan Mahasiswa dalam Menyelesaikan Soal HOTS di Jurusan Pendidikan Fisika Universitas Papua. *Jurnal Komunikasi Pendidikan*, 2 (1), 42-49.
- Suryani, A. (2017). I am an Old Car, My Engine is not Powerful Anymore A Senior Teacher's Voice on His ICT Learning, Obstacles and Its' Implications for Teachers' Development. *International Journal of Pedagogy and Teacher Education (IJPTE)*, 1 (2), 174-188.
- Yusuf, I. and Subaer, S. (2013). Pengembangan Perangkat Pembelajaran Fisika berbasis Media Laboratorium Virtual pada Materi Dualisme Gelombang Partikel di SMA Tut Wuri Handayani Makassar. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 2 (2), 189-194.
- Yusuf, I., Widyaningsih, S. W. and Purwati, D. (2015). Pengembangan Perangkat Pembelajaran Fisika Modern Berbasis Media Laboratorium Virtual berdasarkan Paradigma Pembelajaran Abad 21 dan Kurikulum 2013. *Pancaran Pendidikan*, 4 (2), 189-200.
- Iksan, Z. H. and Saufian, S. M. (2017). Mobile Learning: Innovation in Teaching and Learning using Telegram. *International Journal of Pedagogy and Teacher Education (IJPTE)*, 1 (1), 19-26.
- Gunga, S. O. and Ricketts, I. W. (2007). Facing the Challenges of E-learning Initiatives in African Universities. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 38 (5), 896-906.
- Proudfoot, D. E. and Kebritchi, M. (2017). Scenario-Based E-learning and STEM Education: A Qualitative Study Exploring The Perspectives of Educators. *International Journal of Cognitive Research in Science, Engineering and Education (IJCRSEE)*, 5 (1), 7-18.
- Popovici, A. and Mironov, C. (2015). Students' Perception on Using E-learning Technologie. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 180, 1514-1519.

- Tubaishat, A. and Lansari, A. (2011). Are Students Ready to Adopt E-learning? A Preliminary E-readiness Study of a University in the Gulf Region. *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Research*, 1 (5), 210-215.
- Hake, R. R. (1998). Interactive-Engagement versus Traditional Methods: A Six-Thousand-Student Survey of Mechanics Test Data for introductory Physics Courses. *American Journal of Physics*, 66 (1), 64-74.
- Hake, R. (2002). Relationship of Individual Student Normalized Learning Gains in Mechanics with Gender, High-School Physics, and Pretest Score on Mathematics and Spatial Visualization. *Journal International Indiana University*, 1 (1), 22-34.
- Cohen, J. (1992). A power primer. *Psychological Bulletin*, 112 (1), 155-159.
- Boone, W. J., Staver, J. R. and Yale, M. S. (2014). *Rasch Analysis in the Human Sciences*. Springer Dordrecht Heidelberg, New York London, 2pp. 2-4.
- Gordillo, A., Barra, E., Gallego, D. and Quemada, J. (2013). *An Online E-learning Authoring Tool to Create Interactive Multi-Device Learning Objects using E-infrastructure Resources*. 2013 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference. Oklahoma City Oklahoma USA, pp. 1-7.
- Azis, A. and Yusuf, I. (2013). Aktivitas dan Persepsi Peserta Didik dalam Implementasi Laboratorium Virtual pada Materi Fisika Modern di SMA. *Berkala Fisika Indonesia*, 5 (2), 37-42.
- and Nunamaker, J. F. (2006). Instructional video in e-learning: Assessing the impact of interactive video on learning effectiveness. *Information and Management*, 43 (1), 15-27.
- J. Lee, J. K. and Lee, W. K. (2008). The Relationship of E-learner's Self-Regulatory Efficacy and Perception of E-learning Environmental Quality. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24 (1), 32-47.
- Saadé, R. G., Morina, D. and Thomas, J. D. E. (2012). Critical Thinking in E-learning Environments. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 28 (5), 1608-1617.
- Muryani, C., Sarwono, and Nugraha, S. (2017). Importance Developing E-learning for High School Students In Sragen Regency, Central Java. *International Journal of Pedagogy and Teacher Education (IJPTE)*, 1 (2), 139-146.
- Tanujaya, B. (2016). Development of An Instrument to Measure Higher Order Thinking Skills in Senior High School Mathematics Instruction. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7 (21), 144-148.
- Blas, T. M. and Fernández, A. S. (2009). The Role of new Technologies in The Learning Process: Moodle as A Teaching Tool in Physics. *Computers & Education*, 52 (1), 35-44.
- Aydin, C. C. and Tirkes, G. (2010). *Open source learning management systems in e-learning and Moodle*. IEEE EDUCON 2010 Conference, Madrid.
- Limongelli, C., Sciarrone, F. and Vaste, G. (2011). Personalized E-learning in Moodle: The Moodle LS System. *Journal of e-Learning and Knowledge Society*, 7 (1), 49-58.